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Challenges and strategies for attracting new geologists: situation analysis and future perspectives

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Abstract: The growing demand for geologists contrasts with declining graduation rates, posing a challenge for talent attraction and retention in the field. This study analyses trends in geology graduates, their career choices, and key factors influencing professional commitment, such as job stability, purpose, and fieldwork engagement. The divide between academic research and industry careers is also explored, along with the increasing shift of students toward other disciplines. Finally, strategies to enhance interest and retention in geology education are proposed, aiming to address the long-term shortage of professionals and ensure the field's sustainability.

Keywords: Geology Education, Talent Retention, Labor Market Integration, Academic vs Industry Careers, Professional Shortage

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1. Introduction

In an era defined by the urgent need for critical raw materials, environmental stewardship, and disaster readiness, the role of geologists has never been more vital. Yet paradoxically, the profession faces a growing talent gap as interest in geology studies steadily declines. This study explores the disparities between the growing demand for geoscience workforce and the insufficient number of geology graduates, focusing on the motivations, perceptions, and aspirations of nowadays students. Many factors such as job security, financial situation, and fieldwork come as key influences on career choices.

By analyzing the socio-economic and institutional actual state affecting geological education, the research also highlights the growing division between the academic pathways and what the industry needs for present day jobs. It will end by proposing some strategies ranging from curriculum reform to stronger actions such as developing the collaboration between industry and academics.

2. Materials and Methods

The main methodology employed in this study was bibliographic research. A broad review of the existing literature was carried out, adding a large array of publications from numerous scientific journals as well as notes from international conferences, institutional websites and press articles. These sources span multiple countries as Ghana, USA, Canada or England, allowing for a widespread and comparative perspective on the topic.

3. Results

In this section, we show the results of our bibliographic research as a list of problems that the professional geological sector faces. We try to describe the problems, their origins and how they might affect the future perspectives of the profession, so in later sections we can discuss possible solutions that may be implemented by both the employers and the educational administration.

3.1 Geologist in Society

Firstly, it is important to define what a geologist is. According to Cambridge, a geologist is “a person who studies geology,” with geology defined as “the study of rocks and similar substances that make up the Earth’s surface.” However, this definition can be debated. Geology has undergone significant changes and diversification, with many new branches emerging, making this definition somehow outdated.

“On paper,” that may be the definition of a geologist, but we aim to dive deeper into the geologist's profile and explore how society perceives the profession. Despite the evolution of the geologist’s role, society still largely associates it with the simple phrase “study of rocks.” This is clearly shown in the work of Rogers *et al.* (2024) [1], where this definition was the

most chosen response in a public survey, appearing twice as often as the second most common answer and significantly more than any other option. It is a reminder of how public perception often differs from the realities of modern science.

To truly understand how the image of the geologist has changed, we just must look at the profile of practicing geologists today, men and woman who have been working for decades and the new generation entering the profession. Who are they? What are their backgrounds? Are they men, women, racialized individuals? Taking Canada as an example, one of the country's most actively supporting geosciences, Scott Jess *et al.* work [2] highlights some of the most striking changes. In all today's working geoscientists, 34.3% identify as women, while in the student community, that number rises to 54.2%. This also occurs with racialized individuals representing 18.4% of current professionals but make up 30.3% of the student population. These changes mark a substantial shift toward a more inclusive profession.

Other studies reinforce this trend. For instance, research conducted by the National Association of Geoscience Teachers in Egger *et al.* (2025) [3] between 2004 and 2016 estimated that women made up less than 30% of the workforce, and racialized individuals accounted for less than 10%. Additionally, Yuhang Yang (2025) [4], based on Informetric data from 1950 to 2015, reported that only 21.74% of geoscientists were women, with men comprising the remaining 78.26%. As Yuhang Yang points out, while gender parity is being approached in several STEM fields, geology continues to lag significantly behind.

These figures remain below the average for STEM fields. A meta-analysis by Ceci *et al.* (2014) [5] found that across all STEM disciplines, the average representation of women was about 28%, highlighting how geology's female representation has historically lagged the broader STEM average.

However, despite these encouraging trends, the current public perception of geologists does not yet reflect this evolving reality as Scott Jess's work show [2]. As we can see in the responses collected by Rogers *et al.* (2024) [1], society still associates the profession with the most outdated stereotypes. Comments such as "It's full of old white men," "Old white men with hammers," "Heavily white male dominated," and "Predominantly filled with white men who hike >10 miles a day and drink a lot," illustrate how integrated this image remains. One respondent even stated, "It's very white, middle class and male, which is really off-putting." This vision, while not representative of the student body or the direction of the profession's future, continues to shape how geology is seen by society today.

Geology has evolved rapidly and is becoming more diverse, yet public perception often lags behind, trapped in old stereotypes. The data clearly show progress—especially the growing presence of women and racialized individuals among the new generations of geoscientists—but these changes are not widely recognized outside the profession. To truly move forward, it is important not only to promote diversity within geology, but also to reshape how society sees the field, highlighting its modern, dynamic, and multidisciplinary nature. Closing this gap is essential if geology is to attract talent that reflects the diversity of today's world.

With this perspective in mind, it is worth asking whether the profile of geologists looks the same everywhere. Do geologists across the globe share similar demographic characteristics and professional experiences, or do cultural, social, and economic contexts shape distinct profiles?

3.2 Geologists Around the World: Is the Profile the Same Everywhere?

Understanding the changing profile of geologists will require a global approach. Countries like Canada have seen some dramatic changes in the gender and racial diversity of the profession; however, to contextualize these changes we must compare to other regions such as USA and Ghana. Cultural, economic, and educational factors vary widely in these regions, which in turn may shape diverse demographic and professional profiles of geologists. This section will assess the data from Ghana, and USA to identify similarities and differences in the geologist workforce on an international level, as our goal has been to illustrate how the profession is changing across the globe.

The trend of being a geologist in the United States has been greatly shaped by the emergence of the petroleum industry, as detailed in Figure 1 taken from the Status of Recent Geoscience Graduates 2021 report by Keane *et al.* (2022) [6]. The rise of oil exploration and production resulted in an expansion of opportunities for geologists for much of the 20th century. But by the 1980s, we saw this trend come to a halt, which in turn limited the employment opportunities for geologists when the petroleum industry contracted. Later on, the number of enrolled students increased again, with some oscillations, until the COVID-19 pandemic produced the next downturn in the resource sector. This trajectory clearly shows the cyclic nature of the profession, which demonstrates similar highs and lows to those of the resource industries. We are currently in a phase of significant scarcity of geologists, which shows again that the cycle is still working.

Figure 1: Number of students enrolled in geoscience high education. [6]

The data and figures have been taken from Keane *et al.* (2022) [6].

The situation in Ghana demonstrates the potential and challenges for geoscience education in development contexts. Ghana has 179 universities and colleges of education, of which there are 104 private universities, 15 public universities, 10 public technical universities, 46 public colleges of education, and 4 private colleges of education (Sapha *et al.*, 2024). [7] Among these, only seven institutions offer programs related to geoscience or earth sciences, that is six in the public system (Figure 2) and one private institution. The undergraduate programs in geoscience annually graduate a total of approximately 300 students in Ghana. Since many tertiary-level scholars become opinion leaders and policymakers who are spotlighted with complex earth-related scientific problems, the need for broadening geoscience literate professionals is clear. It is therefore necessary for geoscience to be recognized and integrated into the curriculum as a general education course in every tertiary institution, both private and public, so that our future leaders are aware that the Earth cannot be seen in isolation without the human interactions present on the planet.

	Program	GL	AGL	ENG	SCI	GEC
UG	Earth Science (Geology)	49%	18%	-	23%	10%
	Earth Science (Applied Geology)	31%	37%	-	22%	10%
KNUST	Geological Engineering	14%	39%	20%	18%	9%
UMaT	Geological Engineering	20%	30%	14%	16%	20%
	Petroleum Geoscience	23%	30%	7%	20%	20%
CKT-UTAS	Earth Science	27%	44%	-	22%	7%

GL, Core Geology courses; AGL, Applied Geology courses; ENG, Engineering courses; SCI, General Science courses (including mathematics); GEC, General Education courses; UG, University of Ghana; KNUST, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology; UMaT, University of Mines and Technology; CKT-UTAS, C.K. Tedam University of Technology and Applied Sciences.

Figure 2: Percentage of courses by category for each Geology program in Ghana’s public universities. [7]

3.3 Current work availability

The geoscience workforce is an important part of numerous industries and sectors, including, but not limited to, environmental management, resource extraction, and pedagogy. Graduates with geoscience degrees seek employment in public institutions, government agencies, and private companies, all in a widespread range of salaries as seen in Figure 3. In many cases, while playing different roles, the particular skills and qualifications of these geoscientists create professional windows for collaboration and interchange across work settings. Knowing where geoscientists tend to find employment is fundamental to understanding the job market and shaping educational programs.

Recent studies conducted from Keane *et al.* (2022) [6] and Wilson (2014) [8] found that almost 50% of geoscience master's graduates ended up in the private sector, while nearly 67% of the geoscience PhD graduates went into academic and teaching. This indicates that those with more advanced degrees may go into research and teaching jobs. Geologists follow many career pathways with their destination usually being dictated by their specific area of expertise (Figure 4). Many are drawn toward research, especially those with an interdisciplinary application or those working in academic or scientific workplaces, as contributing to establishing more knowledge in the Earth sciences. Generalist geologists and those specializing

Starting salaries for graduates who accepted a job in the geosciences

Figure 3: Starting salaries for graduates in geosciences. [8]

Figure 4: Professional sector of graduates’ firsts jobs (right) by field of study in bachelor’s degree (left).

in environmental disciplines often end up within public environmental services, which reflects growing societal interest in specialists who can assist with understanding human-induced climate change, land use, pollution, and sustainability challenges. Marine geologists are more often absorbed into environmental services too, due to their work often being similar to the environmental sector, particularly with coastal erosion, marine ecosystems and seabed monitoring.

Geologists specializing in mineralogy and hydrogeology tend to be employed more often in the private sector. Many of these geologists are active in mining, energy, water resources, and natural resource management industries where this expertise is needed for exploration, extraction, and sustainable use of resources. Geologists with similar backgrounds are also hired into professional, scientific, and technical services that might involve consulting, data interpretation, remote sensing, or geographic information systems. Geologists who focus their expertise on soils typically work in environmental and agricultural areas, very much contributing to projects involving land restoration, assessment of soil quality, and ecological rehabilitation.

Most geologists still find career paths within applicable areas of their training or education, while fewer enter careers in "unconventional" sectors less directly related to geology. Some geologists employed in interdisciplinary research centers or in business institutions have positions based on their scientific training, analytical abilities, and overall approach to scientific exploration. Although these less common careers do occur, they illustrate how geoscience training and the transferable mindset it provides can be applied across a wide range of non-traditional career paths.

3.4 New trends in geology: employment trends in environmental sciences

Already in the last century, as the work of John C. Frye (1971) [9] shows, the protection of the environment and the proper and sustainable use of its resources was seen as a crucial field of work for geologists. Nowadays, these preoccupations have reached every aspect of modern society. It could be assumed that, with the increase of concern in environmental problems, geologist would be seen as the ones mainly responsible for solving them. Consequently, there has been a noticeable shift in the professional employment trends towards environmental sciences, as the studies of the Bureau of Labor Statistics [10] makes evident. They project an increase in the environmental scientist workforce of 7%, 1% higher than other scientist and 3% higher than the total for all occupations. This change goes with the decrease in petroleum and gas employment most significant for master's graduates, as Keane *et al.* (2022) [6] shows (Figure 5).

It is evident, that the geology community has understood its role in the fight against climate change and environmental disasters, but this does not apply in the view of the geologist by the general public. As we showed previously in section 3.1, the work of Rogers *et al.* (2024) [1] again serves as an example of the poor knowledge that people unrelated to geology have in this matter. Not only is geology not seen as part of the field of studies that try to protect the environment, but it is seen as a destructive practice due to its connection to oil, gas and mining industries, which have had connotations when talking about the environment. This is another reason for improving the image of geologist in the media, as the public should be aware of the efforts that many geoscientists put into facing these challenges.

3.5 Status of the workforce

We find ourselves at an important moment for the professional geology community. As Ovadia (2008) [11] explains, the demographics of the job pool for geology sciences are dominated by the Baby Boom generation, which are now reaching the retirement age. These losses should be balanced by the input from new graduates. Nevertheless, as we have explained in previous sections, enrolment and consequent graduations are at a low point compared to previous generations. Furthermore, we may check the skills acquired by the students in their academic career to further compare with the skills requested for professional geologist. The Status of Geoscience Graduates recorded by the American Geoscience Institute has an extensive report on the curriculum and experience of recently graduate students in the US. We can observe how basic geological knowledge, like Surface Processes and Earth Materials have the most exposition in the bachelor's degrees

Figure 5: Proportion of employed master's graduates by sectors in the U.S. between 2013 and 2020. [6]

Figure 6: Computational skill intensity of bachelor's graduates.

Figure 7: Correlation matrix between skills requested in geosciences jobs offers.

[12]

tion. Fixing them requires closer collaboration between education and professionals.

For better understanding on the actual mismatch, we will use the amazing work of Shafer *et al.* (2023) [12], which shows an extensive work of job offers and skills required. Field skills are the most frequently requested by employers across nearly all geoscience occupations, except for positions such as GIS analysts, communication specialists, data analysts, computer scientists, and educators. Most job offers require skills such as fieldwork abilities, written communication, project planning, data collection, and driving.

Originally, geoscience curricula embedded fieldwork components, often requiring students to complete field courses before graduation. While this was compulsory for nearly all programs, a recent study has shown that between 2009 and 2022 only half of geology programs currently require a field camp course. The COVID-19 pandemic imposed the use of online or virtual field courses, allowing students to meet graduation requirements despite restrictions. The outcomes of presential fieldwork include essential skills such as data collection and interpretation, written and oral communication, teamwork, and planning, all frequently searched by employers. Although specific skills like documenting field activities, geologic mapping, and field safety are community-defined learning outcomes, they appear less often in job advertisements as they are collateral to the development of professional activity.

Quantitative skills, while requested in only 25% of adverts, tend to be more important where those adverts are linked to project management and data interpretation. These skills are more commonly required for higher-level positions rather than entry-level roles. Employers recognize quantitative abilities as important for career advancement, even if they are not always a prerequisite for initial hiring.

Planning skills appear in over half of job adverts and are frequently emphasized. These skills are linked to teamwork, task management, and budgeting. While not always explicitly taught, many students practice planning through team projects but not as a proper skill. Given employer demand, geoscience programs should consider giving more importance to planning skills.

Communication skills are the most searched in the group of the non-technical skills across all geoscience adverts. Written communication, especially report writing, is requested in two-thirds of job ads, while oral communication appears in nearly half. Although students frequently practice these skills in their courses, many recent graduates still lack writing abilities, showing the need for continued emphasis on communication training in geoscience programs.

Employers recognize system thinking as an important skill, but it rarely appears explicitly in job adverts. Instead, employers may express this necessity by requesting a combination of related skills such as data collection, analysis, interpretation, and problem-solving within Earth systems.

More than half of job ads require a valid driver's license, often to travel to field sites, but sometimes without explanation. Physical ability requirements, such as lifting heavy weights or hiking, appear in about one-third of adverts but are not always directly related to job tasks.

programs. Also, Climate Change is a subject to which many students consider a high priority in their education. Of course, field courses are often considered the cornerstone of geological education, and as such only 20% of the students ends their degree with no field experience. It is interesting to remark the low exposure to data related skills, both in analysis and especially computational languages (Figure 6). Most of the skills' exposure mentioned in Keane *et al.* (2022) [6] is highly improved in master's and PhD studies, except for the computational skills, which still maintain a general low exposure. As we explain in the next chapter, most of the jobs offers request field skills, as well as data analysis and management, for which in modern science some computational skills are required.

3.6 Actual Job offers

Although the number of graduates is slowly growing, employers often report a difference between the skills needed and the ones acquired during academic training. These gaps can limit employability and slow down workforce integra-

The most common skill combinations (Figure 7) searched in geoscience entry-level positions include long-term project management with some quantitative skills if possible, driving paired normally with oral communication, and field skills joined with data collection and record keeping. These combinations prove the multifaceted nature of geoscience roles

In summary, the demand for geoscience professionals shows a wide range of crucial skills, with fieldwork, communication, planning, and data-related abilities as the most important ones. Furthermore, quantitative and systems thinking skills are also valued, but they tend to be more relevant for advanced roles, not at the entry level. The importance of driving and physical requirements in job adverts raises important considerations for accessibility even making unintentionally lose some talent. Overall, the combinations of technical and soft skills reflect the complex and interdisciplinary nature of geoscience careers.

3.7 Current supply issue

The growing demand for geoscience professionals, caused by workforce retirements, new environmental challenges, and increased demand for natural resources, is a problem when the supply of qualified graduates is not enough. The expected cycle of workforce renovation appears to not being working effectively, as enrollment in geoscience programs is still low in many regions, and the rate of degree completion is insufficient to meet the needs. This gap is compounded by economic difficulties and institutional budget cuts, which limit the capacity of universities to expand or improve geoscience education. Due to this, the curriculum of recently graduated students does not meet the criteria requested in most job offers, mostly in data analysis and management skills.

To sum up, the previous sections have shown the paradox that geology faces: while the profession is diversifying and gaining relevance in areas such as environmental management and sustainable resource exploration, public perception remains tied to outdated stereotypes. In general, access to geoscience education is uneven, and the labour market reveals both new opportunities and significant skill gaps, particularly in data analysis and digital management. At the same time, generational renewal is compromised by low enrollment rates, the retirement of experienced professionals, and the persistent mismatch between academic training and the competencies most demanded in job offers. Addressing this imbalance will require a comprehensive strategy that combines stronger promotion of the profession, curricular adaptation, economic incentives, and closer collaboration between universities, industry, and practicing geologists.

4. Discussion

The discussion addresses potential ways to respond to the challenges identified in the previous section. Rather than focusing only on the difficulties, it considers strategies to attract and retain talent within geology and examines the roles that universities, industry, and professional organizations can play. The aim is to outline practical approaches that not only improve career opportunities for new geologists but also strengthen the long-term sustainability of the profession.

4.1 Possible improvements by employers

Until now, the focus of this study has been mainly directed towards the new workforce entering the field of geology, as well as the tendencies and skills. However, we have not focused on the role of the companies doing the hiring and the professionals already working within them. The progress and improvement of geology as a discipline cannot rely only on the arms of the younger generation, so, it must be understood as a collaborative effort between the new professionals and the experienced geologists who are already part of the industry.

This means that the integration and professional growth of young geologists will only be possible if current geologists, particularly those occupying positions within companies, actively support and encourage them. Senior geologists must not only recognize the potential of new talent but also act as mentors, providing guidance, opportunities, and a professional environment where innovative ideas can be tested and developed. Without this generational cooperation, geology risks starvation, as new professionals may lack somewhere to put their knowledge.

Therefore, the responsibility for the advancement of geology must be seen as a dual commitment. Young geologists can contribute with fresh and new perspectives, different and updated academic knowledge, and promoting the use of new technologies, while experienced geologists can contribute with their practical expertise, understanding of the industry, and the ability to connect the theory learned in the academic institutions with real industrial applications.

It may seem easy to ask for better working conditions or greater recognition. Improved salaries, fairer contracts, and more favorable conditions would make the profession more attractive, even to those who currently do not perceive geology as a promising career path. However, while these aspects are undoubtedly important, they cannot be considered a definitive or long-lasting solution.

The reason is straightforward: financial incentives and external benefits are limited. When companies face budget restrictions or economic downturns—as they inevitably will—such improvements are placed at risk. If the development of geology depends primarily on financial measures, its progress will remain closely tied to economic cycles and market volatility. Moreover, because geology is strongly associated with the land, it is also highly susceptible to geopolitical shifts.

What is needed instead is a structural change, one that focuses not only on rewards but also on active collaboration, mentorship, and long-term investment in knowledge and innovation. Only through these more lasting measures can geology strengthen its base.

In this study, we propose that one possible path toward meaningful improvement lies in redefining how salaries are structured for geologists. Rather than being based on traditional pay scales or common industry standards, compensation could be based in modern parameters such as efficiency, productivity, and the necessary and important contributions of

geologists to their projects. At the same time, it is important to recognize that all geological branches cannot be evaluated in the exact same way as other disciplines. The nature of geological work is unique, and this uniqueness must be reflected in the way geologists are valued and rewarded.

Of course, the responsibilities of geologists vary depending on their specific role. However, one aspect remains common across most positions: fieldwork. Fieldwork is not only the principal duty for many geologists, but it is also one of the most demanding aspects of the profession. Distinct from office-based tasks, fieldwork often requires long hours in remote locations, exposure to difficult weather conditions or extended periods away from family. These realities transform the practice of geology into a particularly challenging occupation that demands both technical expertise and physical strength.

Therefore, we suggest that this dimension of geological work should be given greater consideration when structuring compensation models for geologists. A fair recognition of the unique demands of fieldwork would not only provide a more accurate reflection of the geologist's contribution but would also contribute to making the profession more attractive in the long term.

This idea has already been partially applied in certain regions through the well-known "FIFO" (Fly-In Fly-Out) system, particularly popular in Australia, where it has become a standard approach to managing geological and mining labour. Under this model, companies understand that geology cannot always be measured by the same standards of productivity or efficiency that are applied to other professions. The reason lies in a fundamental and unavoidable reality: the physical demands of the job. Unlike many disciplines where work can be carried out in offices or remotely, geologists often must physically travel to far sites, leaving behind their everyday environment and focusing themselves fully to the field.

This requirement creates an inherent barrier that no technological advancement or productivity strategy can eliminate for now. Fieldwork inevitably involves displacement, adaptation to different environments, and the acceptance of long shifts under conditions that may be physically and mentally challenging. Furthermore, this challenge also extends to student mobility after graduation. In Spain, only 14.2% of undergraduates and 26.7% of master's students move to another region, while just 14.1% of graduates work outside the region where they studied, according to Europa Press. (2018) [13] At the European level, around 10.9% of graduates have experienced some form of international mobility, though rates range from 79.6% in Luxembourg and 28.6% in Cyprus to less than 5% in Italy and Poland, as stated by the European Commission (2024). [14] In the Netherlands, 57% of international graduates remain one year after graduation, with STEM graduates showing particularly high retention, as reported by Nuffic. (2025) and Erudera. (2024). [15,16] In the United Kingdom, 46.5% of graduates stay in their home region, 22.4% return after studying elsewhere, and 31.1% work in a different region altogether, according to HESA (2022) and Medunić *et al.* (2022). [17,18] The FIFO system is one way companies have attempted to balance these demands by offering attractive financial incentives and structured rotations, making the profession not only economically rewarding but also more manageable for those willing to embrace its challenges.

Nevertheless, while FIFO demonstrates that companies can adapt compensation models to the unique realities of geological work, it also raises broader questions about sustainability, well-being, and the long-term attractiveness of the profession. Relying solely on financial rewards may not be sufficient.

Therefore, we propose that companies hiring new geologists should consider the true nature of the profession and what it really means to be a geologist. This understanding cannot come just from management or external observation, it must also be shaped and demonstrated by the professionals who are currently working in the field. As we have already pointed out, the industry is facing a growing shortage of geologists, and without a clear recognition of the demands and realities of the profession, this shortage may only deepen.

One specific measure that could represent a step forward would be fairer compensation of field hours. Fieldwork is not just another task; it is often the backbone of geological practice, requiring significant personal and physical effort. In today's society, where remote work and digital solutions are increasingly common and many professions demand less physical presence, the value of this active and challenging work should not be underestimated. By acknowledging and rewarding the distinctive contributions of geologists in the field, companies could not only improve job satisfaction and retention but also make the profession more attractive to future generations

4.2 Skill disparities

When comparing the training offered in geology degrees with the skills most frequently requested in job advertisements, several mismatches become evident. Undergraduate programs tend to emphasize basic geological knowledge, such as surface processes, earth materials, and climate change, as well as fieldwork, which remains central to geological education. Most students graduate with at least some field experience, and this training provides also some competencies in data collection, interpretation, teamwork, and communication. These abilities align closely with what employers continue to value most, particularly in entry-level roles.

Nevertheless, important gaps persist. Data-related abilities, like computational analysis and programming, are still underrepresented in geology study programs. Even though they become slightly more visible in master's and doctoral studies, they remain weak compared to the growing demand for data management and quantitative skills in professional practice. This is consistent with wider debates in science education: Medunić *et al.* (2022) [19] argue that programming in languages such as Python not only builds technical competence but also helps critical thinking and interdisciplinary problem-solving, making it an essential component of modern scientific training. Similarly, planning and communication, two of the most common requirements in job offers, are often treated in academic programs as side effects of teamwork or coursework rather than as explicit learning objectives. This results in graduates who may have some exposure to these skills but often lack the depth employers expect.

It is also worth noting that some requirements frequently found in job advertisements, such as holding a valid driver's license or meeting certain physical demands, fall outside the scope of university training. These expectations are understandable within professional contexts, yet it is evident that such abilities cannot be meaningfully developed in an academic environment. Instead, they highlight the practical realities of geological work beyond the classroom.

Taken together, these disparities show that geology degrees provide a strong foundation in knowledge and fieldwork but lag behind in preparing students for the interdisciplinary, data-driven, and skill-diverse profiles sought in the labour market. Bridging this gap will require curricular reforms that integrate computational tools, structured training in planning and communication, with a closer alignment between academic outcomes and industry needs. In this context, Medunić *et al.* (2022) [19] advocate for a new branch in geological training, termed “computational geosciences”, in which programming, data science methods, and mathematical modeling become core curriculum pillars, not optional or advanced electives. They argue that such integration is essential because of the digitalization of science, richer datasets, and the rise of machine learning demand that geoscientists are fluent not only in field techniques, but also in algorithmic analysis and quantitative reasoning.

4.3 Geologist working in other areas

Every well-formed geologist is aware of the diversity of opportunities that this science offers in the professional context. From environmental management to civil construction and even planetary exploration, geologists are equipped with knowledge that enables them to perform a wide range of tasks. Nevertheless, as we mentioned in section 3.2, most geologists end up working in fields where their basic academic training is most applicable. Giving greater visibility to the multidisciplinary side of geological sciences may therefore be another way of attracting more students to this field.

We can observe this trend in China, where many universities are beginning to implement such approaches. For example, Niu *et al.* (2022) [20] at Hefei University of Technology and Liu *et al.* (2022) [21] at Guangdong University of Petrochemical Technology describe reforms focused on technological advances and the integration of artificial intelligence. The study from Guangdong points to issues already highlighted in previous sections, such as the mismatch between university curricula and the skills demanded by industry. To address this, the university proposes several curricular changes, including the integration of AI and advanced modelling techniques, so that graduates acquire knowledge increasingly valued in geology-related industries. At Hefei University, similar reforms have already been implemented as a response to the ongoing shift from traditional earth science to Earth System Science. Their approach emphasizes diversified training models aimed at cultivating innovative and interdisciplinary talent. In particular, they advocate stronger connections between geology and emerging fields such as big data, new engineering, and planetary exploration.

In Europe, similar initiatives already exist in programs that connect geology with space sciences and digital technologies. The TU Bergakademie Freiberg in Germany offers a pioneering B.Sc. in Space Resources [22], focused on planetary exploration and *in-situ* resource utilization. The Freie Universität Berlin provides a *M.Sc. in Planetary Sciences and Space Exploration* [23], while the Erasmus Mundus program GeoPlaNet EMJM in Planetary Geosciences [24] gives students the chance to specialize in planetary geology across several European universities. Beyond the planetary domain, programs such as the Copernicus Master in Digital Earth [25] and the M.Sc. in Geo-information Science & Earth Observation at the University of Twente [26] highlight the potential of combining geology with geoinformatics, data science, and Earth observation. These examples show how expanding geology education into multidisciplinary areas not only enriches curricula but also broadens graduates' career prospects.

Other fields would also benefit from an interdisciplinary approach in geology, particularly climate change, already mentioned in section 3.3. Stubbs *et al.* (2017) [27] showed that multidisciplinary design teams are more effective in creating activities that integrate different disciplines, incorporate a diversity of scientific perspectives, and take into account instructional design choices. This suggests that not only industry, but also public research institutions could benefit from a stronger multidisciplinary training of geologists.

We believe that applying and giving more visibility to these shifts towards new and exciting fields of study could help make geology much more attractive to newer generations of students. Strengthening the multidisciplinary dimension of geology is not only a matter of academic reform but also of perception: by highlighting its connections to planetary sciences, digital technologies, climate change, and sustainable development, geology can be seen as a discipline that actively engages with some of the most pressing challenges of our time. This broader perspective may both attract students with diverse interests and ensure that future geoscientists are prepared to contribute meaningfully across traditional and emerging fields.

4.4 Geology in the current generations

Entertainment media have a strong capacity to educate adults about science, as noted by Dahlstrom (2014). [28] However, they can also produce unintended consequences, reinforcing negative stereotypes about specific disciplines. A well-known example is *The Big Bang Theory*, where the character Sheldon Cooper repeatedly mocks geology, portraying it as less rigorous than physics and other sciences. Though this is humorous, it entrenches the widespread perception of geology as a “soft” or secondary science (Forlenza, 2014). [29].

Such portrayals are particularly influential for younger audiences. Studies in science communication indicate that media representations play a pivotal role in shaping how students perceive scientific disciplines and in influencing their early career choices. When geology is wrongly depicted as irrelevant or trivial, younger generations may be discouraged from considering it a serious field of study. This, combined with existing enrolment challenges in the geosciences, could reduce the number of students pursuing geology degrees, thereby affecting the discipline's long-term sustainability (Stewart & Lewis, 2017). [30]

At the same time, other fields within the geosciences have benefitted from highly successful media portrayals. Paleontology, in particular, saw a surge in public interest and visibility following the release of *Jurassic Park* (1993) and its sequels. This franchise inspired widespread fascination with dinosaurs and motivated many to pursue careers in paleontology, as McLoughlin (2025) noted. [31] While the films contained inaccuracies, they heightened the cultural status of paleontology and demonstrate how positive, dramatic media representations can spark genuine curiosity and influence academic interests.

Geology has not yet enjoyed a similar blockbuster moment, but educators have devised creative strategies to leverage popular media effectively. For example, Jonathan Nyquist at Temple University teaches a course titled *Disasters: Geology vs. Hollywood*, which uses clips from disaster films—such as *Dante's Peak*, *Aftershock*, and *Armageddon*—to expose misconceptions, foster student discussion, and deepen understanding of geological phenomena (Nyquist, 2025). [32] This method can enhance student engagement and reinforce core geoscientific concepts.

Despite these successes, geoscientists still face significant challenges when engaging with mass media. Geological processes often involve abstract concepts or vast timescales that are difficult to communicate clearly. Additionally, as Liverman (2008) [33] portrays, politically sensitive topics, such as resource extraction or climate change, complicate communication, and some scientists fear that engaging with media may harm their academic reputation—a concern known as the “Sagan effect”. [30] Therefore, it is crucial to involve geologists directly in television and media productions, ensuring their expertise and presence contribute to accurate, attractive portrayals of Earth sciences. Doing so enhances public trust, makes the discipline more appealing to younger audiences, and encourages aspiring students to see geology as dynamic and relevant. Initiatives like the *Science & Entertainment Exchange* from the National Academy of Sciences (USA) illustrate how meaningful collaborations between scientists and content creators can yield richer, more scientifically sound portrayals.

4.5 Geology improving in the media

As technology continues to advance, many new ways for sharing ideas and promoting disciplines have been raised, and one of the most important ones of them is social media. In today's world, almost everything is posted and shared online, often serving as an amazing tool of visibility and attraction (Bik & Goldstein, 2013). [34] Despite its potential, social media has not been widely used in geology. This lack of presence can be seen as a missed opportunity, particularly when compared with other fields that have successfully used digital platforms to show their relevance and connect with new workforce, as stated by King (2019). [35]

Historically, geology has often stayed behind in adopting new technologies compared to other scientific disciplines, and this tendency has been one of the main causes of the limited public perception the discipline has today. By not positioning itself in the digital sphere, geology risks continue having an outdated image of being traditional and disconnected from today's advancements. However, this challenge can also be seen as an opportunity. Social media offers geology a way to highlight its importance, promote career opportunities, and connect with younger generations as other disciplines have done before (Allgaier, 2016). [36]

Promoting geology should not be limited to showing its scientific contributions only. It is as important as is the promotion of the geologist's way of life, with all its challenges and rewards. It is true that geology is not always the most physically comfortable type of work, as it often requires demanding fieldwork. These realities can make the profession seem less attractive compared to careers that are more sedentary, flexible, or technological.

However, this same lifestyle also carries unique elements that, if well promoted, could serve as powerful attractions. The opportunity to work outdoors, to travel, to discover and interpret the Earth firsthand, and to contribute directly to solving resource and environmental challenges are experiences that few other professions can offer.

When discussing the lifestyle of geologists, it is important to recognize not only the challenges but also the benefits that fieldwork has. Beyond the physical demands, fieldwork enhances strength and a healthy active lifestyle that contrasts with the sedentary nature of many modern professions. Perhaps the opportunity of travelling is even more significant. For many geologists, their career leads them to experiences in diverse locations, ranging from remote natural landscapes to culturally rich regions. As many senior geologists will recall, nearly everyone in the field has a colleague, or has been that colleague themselves, who has traveled extensively in different countries and contributing to relevant projects. This adventurous dimension of geology, when properly communicated, can become one of the discipline's strongest calling cards for attracting new generations.

Another important perspective that could be highlighted through media is the alignment of geology with some popular trends that are already becoming stronger in society. In recent years, movements with ideas such as “reconnecting with the nature,” “returning to the wilderness,” have gained traction. These ideas promote outdoor experiences and a lifestyle that breaks down with the monotony of purely urban and office-based routines. Geology could become the perfect discipline for people who commute with this philosophy.

Geology, in many ways, naturally embodies these values. Geology makes individuals contact directly with the Earth, often in environments far from the conventional desktop workspaces. By positioning geology as more than just a scientific discipline, by showing it as a way of life that joins exploration, outdoor activity, and a deeper connection with nature, it could resonate with wider audiences and attract those who are seeking adventure in their careers.

One of the most powerful impacts that social media could have on geology is the transformation of its public image. For too long, the “typical geologist” has been associated with outdated stereotypes, often male, working in oil or extractive industries, and engaged in activities perceived as environmentally destructive. However, this image no longer reflects the full reality of the profession. Today, geology has increased its diversity, inclusivity. By promoting these changes, social media can play a key role in showing that geology is not only open to different races, genders, and backgrounds, but is also evolving to align with global priorities.

This shift can be illustrated by the transition many companies have made over the last decades, moving away from the traditional oil-driven image and towards environmentally conscious practices, renewable resources, and innovative mining techniques that aim to minimize impact. Highlighting these transformations could help break long-standing misconceptions and present geology as a discipline that is deeply relevant to modern challenges such as climate change, sustainable development, and the responsible use of natural resources.

In this sense, social media offers geology a unique chance to take the lead in public communication. The rise of podcasts, blogs, video channels, and digital communities dedicated to science communication demonstrates that audiences are eager to engage with disciplines when they are presented in accessible and inspiring ways. [34, 36] An example of these new ways of promotion could be podcast or channels such as “Pakozoico” or “Huellas de la montaña”. There are already geologists beginning to use these platforms to share insights, experiences, and visions of what the field can become. However, this is an opportunity that must be seized soon. If geology fails to step forward in the coming years, other narratives may dominate the conversation, leaving the discipline once again in the background.

4.6 New future of geology

As was mentioned earlier, geology has been behind in the use of new technologies. While this has been seen as a disadvantage, it can also be seen as an opportunity. By embracing modern tools and techniques, geologists could have the potential to enhance their skills, improve their efficiency, and expand the impact of their work (van der Krogt *et al.*, 2020). [37]

There are numerous areas in geology where technology can be applied. For instance, drones and advanced cartography can improve data collection and mapping in remote or difficult-to-access areas. Modeling software allows for more precise simulations of geological processes, while geotechnical modeling can improve infrastructure planning and resource management (Colomina & Molina, 2014 and McClintock *et al.*, 2017). [38, 39] Modeling hydrological masses and their analysis can deepen our understanding of underground water systems. Flood control or water resource management could be maybe the more important as the impacts of flood are the most brutal in all the hazardous geological processes. These examples demonstrate that, when there is a good use of technology, it can not only modernize geology but also expand its relevance.

Currently, only a limited number of companies are developing different types of advanced geological software, even though their use is already common in research centers according to Turner (2021). [40] This gap underscores an opportunity for the industry to modernize in some respects, adopting technologies that can improve efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance decision-making. By closing the divide between research innovation and practical applications, companies can get competitive advantages and contribute to developing the discipline.

The adoption and effective use of these technologies is in the hands of the new generation entering the discipline, as stated by Aral & Weill (2007) and Huyghe *et al.* (2022). [41, 42] Young geologists have the opportunity, and furthermore the responsibility, to explore, experiment, and manage these tools to implement technological advancements, in the field. By the use of modern software, modelling techniques, and digital tools, they can help close the gap between research innovations and practical applications in industry. As a consequence of that, geology has the potential to reach an important level of technological advance as other scientific and engineering disciplines have developed in the last decades.

There will always be the challenges of fieldwork, the physical demands, remote locations, and hard and changing conditions, but improving work efficiency is in hands of the exploration and application of new technologies. This represents a vast undiscovered territory for geologists, offering new opportunities for young geologists who are interested not only in traditional geological work but also in technological advancements. Using tools such as drones, modelling software, remote sensing, and advanced data analytics, these new professionals can help transform fieldwork from a physically demanding barrier into a more productive, efficient, and less tedious process, pushing the discipline forward both scientifically and technologically (Gómez & Pardo-Igúzquiza, 2016). [43]

4.7 Real consequences of the lack of geologist

The shortage of geologists will have consequences that go far beyond the discipline itself. Geology makes a massive contribution to society, from understanding natural resources and hazards to sustainable land use and environmental protection (Gill, 2017 and Stewart & Gill, 2017). [44, 45] There simply cannot be a future without continued exploration and study of the Earth, despite the misconception that some have that “everything has already been discovered in geology.”

A progressive reduction in the workforce risks producing geologists who are less trained or trying to convert professionals from other scientific areas into geology without the proper foundation (King, 2008) and Whitmeyer & Mogk, 2009). [46, 47] While these individuals may bring valuable skills, it’s not probable that they will match the expertise and depth of knowledge that geologists can achieve. Over time, this could lower the quality, reliability, and innovation of the discipline.

We are already seeing the consequences of a shortage of geologists, and many examples have appeared in the news. One recent and close case is the Dana disaster in Valencia, where better advice from geologists working in the area before the disaster and more thorough studies might had helped mitigate the impacts. Similar tragedies, such as numerous deadly landslides in various parts of the world being constantly in the news, show everyone how important geological knowledge in planning and establishing habitable areas, risk assessment, and disaster prevention could be (van Westen, 2006 and Glade *et al.*, 2005). [48, 49]

These events show that the undervaluation of geologists can have real and destroying effects on society, highlighting the urgent need to strengthen the discipline, invest in professional expertise, and ensure that geological advice is integrated into decision-making processes.

5. Conclusion

This study has highlighted the paradox that geology faces today: while demand for geoscientists is rising, enrollment and graduation rates are insufficient. Public perception still relies on outdated stereotypes, discouraging new students. Although diversity is increasing, this progress is not yet reflected in society's image of the profession. Academic programs remain strong in field training but fall short in data, computational, and communication skills demanded by the industry. Lastly, generational renewal is threatened by retirements and low graduate numbers.

Geology holds great potential in emerging fields (environment, AI, geoinformatics, planetary sciences) and has always had a crucial role in sectors like civil engineering or the exploitation of primary resources. Nevertheless, curricula and outreach must adapt to face the new era of high-tech and social media.

Sustaining the professional sector will require an integrated strategy including: curricular reforms, closer academia–industry collaboration, economic incentives for new employees, mentoring from more experienced generations, and stronger media presence to reshape geology's image and engage with the newer generations of students.

References

- Rogers, S. L., Giles, S., Dowey, N., Greene, S. E., Bhatia, R., Van Landeghem, K., & King, C. (2024). "you just look at rocks, and have beards" Perceptions of Geology From the United Kingdom: A Qualitative Analysis From an Online Survey. *Earth Sci. Syst. Soc.* 4:10078. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.3389/esss.2024.10078>.
- Jess, S., Heer, E., & Schoenbohm, L. (2025). Research students are diverse, while those in salaried positions are not: Results from a survey of Canadian academic geoscience. *Earth Science, Systems and Society*, 5(1), esss2024-013. <https://doi.org/10.1144/esss2024-013>
- Egger, A.E., Viskupic, K., and Iverson, E.R. (2019). Results of the National Geoscience Faculty Survey (2004-2016). National Association of Geoscience Teachers, Northfield, MN. 82 p.
- Yang, Y., Zhang, C., Xu, H., Bu, Y., Liu, M., & Ding, Y. (2025). Gender differences in dropout rate: From field, career status, and generation perspectives. *Journal of Informetrics*, 19(1), 101615. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2024.101615>
- Ceci, S. J., Ginther, D. K., Kahn, S., & Williams, W. M. (2014). Women in academic science: A changing landscape. *Psychological science in the public interest*, 15(3), 75-141.
- Keane, C., Gonzales, L., & Robinson, D. (2022). Status of Recent Geoscience Graduates. American Geosciences Institute. (ISBN: 978-0-922152-54-4)
- Sapah, M. S., Asiedu, D. K., & Loh, Y. S. A. (2024). Geoscience education in Ghana: Status and recommendations. *International Union of Geological Sciences*, 47(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.18814/epiugs/2023/023012>.
- Wilson, C. (2014). Status of Recent Geoscience Graduates 2014. American Geosciences Institute. (ISBN: 978-0-922152-99-3)
- Frye, John C. (1971). A geologist views the environment. *Environmental Geology Notes*, 42. Illinois State Geological Survey, Urbana.
- Bureau of Labor Statistics, U.S. Department of Labor, *Occupational Outlook Handbook*, Environmental Scientists and Specialists. Available online: <https://www.bls.gov/ooh/life-physical-and-social-science/environmental-scientists-and-specialists.htm> (accessed on 13th September, 2025).
- Ovadaia, D (2008) Are there enough geologist in the world to meet demand? Proceedings of the 45th CCOP Annual Session, Khon Kaen, Thailand, 23 – 28 November 2008.
- Shafer, G.W., Viskupic, K., and Egger, A.E., 2023, Critical workforce skills for bachelor-level geo scientists: An analysis of geoscience job advertisements: *Geosphere*, v. 19, no. 2, p. 628– 644, <https://doi.org/10.1130/GES02581.1>.
- Europa Press. (2018, 27th December). *El 26,7 % de los alumnos de máster estudian fuera de su comunidad, casi el doble que en los títulos de grado*. Europa Press. Available online: <https://www.europapress.es/sociedad/educacion-00468/noticia-267-alumnos-master-estudian-fuera-comunidad-casi-doble-titulos-grado-20181227133012.html>.
- European Commission. (2024). *Education and Training Monitor 2024*. Publications Office of the European Union. DOI : <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2766/815875>.
- Nuffic. (2025). *Stay rates of international graduates in the Netherlands*. Nuffic. Available online: <https://www.nuffic.nl/en/stayrates-of-international-graduates>.
- Erudera. (2024). *40% of STEM graduates in the Netherlands stay after graduation, compared to 19% in social sciences*. Erudera. Available online : <https://erudera.com/news/40-of-international-stem-students-stay-in-netherlands-after-graduation>.
- Jack, P. (2022, 29 de noviembre). *Returning home after graduation? It's more complicated*. *Times Higher Education*. Available online : <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/news/returning-home-after-graduation-its-more-complicated>.
- Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA). (2022). *Graduate Outcomes: Graduates salaries and work location*. HESA.
- Medunić, G., Chakravarty, S., & Kundu, R. (2022). Computational skills in geosciences higher education system for the 21st century. *Mathematical methods and terminology in geology* 2022, 5-12.
- Niu Manlan, Xu Liqiang, Sun Yi, Li Xiucui, Xie Jiancheng, Li Jiahao, Shen Yuefeng (2022). Thinking and Practice from Curriculum Reform of the Course "Physical Geology" under the New Circumstance. *Geological Journal of China Universities*, 28(3): 347-351.
- Zhe Liu, Jiajing Li and Wei Wang, Exploration on the Construction Reform of Geology Specialty with Deep Integration of Artificial Intelligence under the New Engineering Background. *Curriculum and Teaching Methodology* (2022) Vol. 5: 33-38. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.23977/curtm.2022.050305>.
- Bachelor Space Resources – Weltraumtechnologien – TU Bergakademie Freiberg. Available online: <https://tu-freiberg.de/en/study/bachelor-space-resources-weltraumtechnologien> (accessed on 6th September 2025).
- Planetary Science and Space Exploration – Freie Universität Berlin. Available online: <https://www.fu-berlin.de/en/studium/studienangebot/master/planetary-sciences-space-exploration/index.html> (accessed on 6th September 2025).
- Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degree in Planetary Geosciences – GeoPlaNet. Available online: <https://geoplanet-impgeu> (accessed on 6th September 2025).
- Copernicus Master in Digital Earth. Available online: <https://master-cde.eu> (accessed on 6th September 2025).

26. Master Geo-information Science & Earth Observation – University of Twente. Available online: <https://www.itc.nl/education/study-finder/geo-information-science-earth-observation> (accessed on 6th September 2025).
27. Stubbs, E.A., Zimmerman, A.R., Warner, L.A. *et al.* (2018). Reflecting on a multidisciplinary collaboration to design a general education climate change course. *J Environ Stud Sci* 8, 32–38. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13412-017-0451-8>
28. Dahlstrom, M. F. (2014). Using narratives and storytelling to communicate science with non-expert audiences. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111(Suppl. 4), 13614–13620.
29. Forlenza, M. (2014). Geologists in Popular Culture. *From the Editor – June 2014, Houston Geological Society*. Available online : <https://www.hgs.org/node/5437>
30. Stewart, I. S., & Lewis, D. (2017). Communicating contested geoscience to the public: Moving from ‘matters of fact’ to ‘matters of concern’. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 174, 122–133.
31. McLoughlin, E. (2025). Jurassic Park’s Impact on Paleontological Tourism: A Conceptual Analysis of Media and Public Perception. *Tourism: An International Interdisciplinary Journal*.
32. Nyquist, J. E. (2025). *Disasters: Geology vs. Hollywood* [Course description]. Temple University.
33. Liverman, D. G. (2008). Environmental geoscience; communication challenges. *Geological Society, London, Special Publications, volume 305*, 197 - 209
34. Bik, H. M., & Goldstein, M. C. (2013). *An introduction to social media for scientists*. PLOS Biology, 11(4), e1001535. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001535>.
35. King, H. (2019). Public perception of geoscience and geoscientists. In C. S. Rosen, D. Mogk, & A. L. Riggs (Eds.), *Geoscience for the public good and global development: Toward a sustainable future* (pp. 13–28). Geological Society of America. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1130/2019.2543\(02\)](https://doi.org/10.1130/2019.2543(02)).
36. Allgaier, J. (2016). *Science on social media: Platforms, audiences, and impact*. Science Communication, 38(4), 405–418. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1075547016632721>.
37. van der Krogt, R., Broekhuijsen, J., & Verweij, H. (2020). *Geoscience in the digital age: Embracing new technologies for research and industry*. Computers & Geosciences, 140, 104498. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2020.104498>.
38. Colomina, I., & Molina, P. (2014). *Unmanned aerial systems for photogrammetry and remote sensing: A review*. ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing, 92, 79–97. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2014.02.013>.
39. McClintock, T., Roberts, J. W., & Green, D. R. (2017). *Applications of UAVs in geosciences: A review*. Geomorphology, 293, 1–15. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2017.04.027>.
40. Turner, D. (2021). *The role of software in the digital transformation of geoscience industries*. Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering, 196, 107815. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petrol.2020.107815>.
41. Aral, S., & Weill, P. (2007). IT assets, organizational capabilities, and firm performance: How resource allocations and organizational differences explain performance variation. *Organization Science*, 18(5), 763–780. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.1070.0306>.
42. Huyghe, P., Malet, J. P., & Travelletti, J. (2022). *Digital transformation in geosciences: Opportunities and challenges*. Computers & Geosciences, 161, 105059. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2022.105059>.
43. Gómez, C., & Pardo-Igúzquiza, E. (2016). *Geostatistics and GIS: Tools for the geosciences*. Earth-Science Reviews, 155, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2016.01.009>.
44. Gill, J. (2017). *Geoscience and society: A brief overview*. Episodes, 40(4), 271–277. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18814/epiiugs/2017/v40i4/017036>.
45. Stewart, I. S., & Gill, J. C. (2017). *Social geology—Integrating sustainability concepts into Earth sciences*. Proceedings of the Geologists' Association, 128(2), 165–172. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pgeola.2017.01.002>.
46. King, C. (2008). *Geoscience education: An overview*. Studies in Science Education, 44(2), 187–222. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057260802264289>.
47. Whitmeyer, S. J., & Mogk, D. W. (2009). *Geoscience field education: A recent resurgence*. Eos, Transactions American Geophysical Union, 90(34), 273–274. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009EO340001>.
48. van Westen, C. J., van Asch, T. W. J., & Soeters, R. (2006). *Landslide hazard and risk zonation—Why is it still so difficult?* Bulletin of Engineering Geology and the Environment, 65(2), 167–184. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10064-005-0023-0>.
49. Glade, T., Anderson, M., & Crozier, M. J. (Eds.). (2005). *Landslide hazard and risk*. John Wiley & Sons.